

The Geometry of Project Dynamics: A Frenet–Serret Trajectory Framework for Monitoring Performance and Systemic Complexity

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Abstract

Purpose

Project monitoring in complex environments is still largely dominated by stage-based Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) and static complexity metrics, which limit managers' ability to interpret structural changes unfolding between reporting milestones. This study addresses this limitation by conceptualizing projects not merely as sequences of states, but as trajectories evolving through a joint performance–complexity space.

Design/methodology/approach

The paper introduces a geometry-based and model-agnostic framework that represents project evolution as a continuous trajectory constructed from discrete KPI and Systemic Complexity Index (SCI) observations. Using the Frenet–Serret formalism, curvature (κ) and torsion (τ) are derived as intrinsic descriptors of project motion. These indicators are obtained by interpolating stage-based monitoring data into a differentiable trajectory and are evaluated at managerial decision points. The framework is illustrated using real project monitoring data.

Findings

The results show that joint κ – τ patterns provide a compact and interpretable description of project regime transitions, structural instability, and stabilization phases. In the empirical

case, peaks in curvature and torsion coincide with periods of strong trade-off conflict and systemic decoupling, while their subsequent reduction reflects restored alignment and governability.

Originality

Rather than proposing a new performance metric or predictive control tool, this study reframes project monitoring as the observation of project motion through a joint performance–complexity space. The SCI–Frenet framework offers a new conceptual and methodological lens that complements existing project control approaches by supporting managerial sensemaking under complexity.

This manuscript is a preprint and has been submitted for peer review. The purpose of this preprint is to establish the date of public disclosure of the proposed framework and to document the originality of applying Frenet–Serret geometry to the field of project management.

Keywords: Project dynamics, Systemic complexity, Frenet-Serret, Geometric indicators, Project performance, Decision Support System, Risk.

1. Introduction

Project management is increasingly conducted in environments marked by uncertainty, interdependence, and non-predicted interactions among technical, organizational, and contextual factors. As a result, project complexity is no longer understood merely as a descriptive attribute, but as a dynamic property that shapes both project outcomes and the effectiveness of managerial interventions (Hu et al., 2023; Poveda-Bautista et al., 2018).

In practice, however, project monitoring and control remain largely dominated by stage-based assessments of Key Performance Indicators (KPIs). While KPIs continue to play a central role in governance and accountability, a growing body of literature highlights their limitations in complex project environments. KPI-based monitoring often provides only partial insight into multi-dimensional performance and may offer limited diagnostic value when projects drift off track, particularly in the presence of strong interdependencies among project elements (Korhonen et al., 2023; Ibrahim et al., 2024; Kumar et al., 2023). Early-warning research further suggests that threshold-based KPI deviations are often insufficient to anticipate emerging instability in complex projects (Soliman et al., 2025).

To complement performance-based monitoring, several approaches have sought to operationalize project complexity more explicitly. Among them, the Systemic Complexity Index (SCI) was introduced as a quantitative diagnostic capable of capturing non-linear interdependencies among critical success factors by integrating performance information, risk exposure, and interaction structures (Peris et al., 2025). SCI provides valuable insight into whether complexity tends to be amplified or compensated as project conditions change. Nevertheless, in its conventional formulation, SCI remains inherently stage-based, yielding discrete observations at predefined checkpoints rather than a continuous representation of project evolution.

This paper builds on these limitations by advancing a different conceptual premise: projects should not be understood solely as sequences of states, but as trajectories evolving through a joint performance–complexity space. From this perspective, what matters is not only where a project is at a given reporting point, but how it is moving through that space, how abruptly it changes direction, and whether its evolution remains structurally coherent across dimensions. This view aligns with process-oriented perspectives on project complexity and with calls to move beyond static representations of project behavior (Williams, 2005).

To operationalize this view, the study proposes a geometric and model-agnostic framework that represents project evolution as a continuous trajectory constructed from discrete KPI and SCI observations. By transforming stage-based data into a smooth curve, the framework enables the application of tools from differential geometry, specifically the Frenet–Serret formalism, to extract intrinsic geometric descriptors of project motion. Frenet-based curvature and torsion have been widely used in engineering and data analysis to characterize changes in trajectory regimes because they provide interpretable invariants of “bending” and “twisting” that go beyond linear trend analysis (Werling et al., 2010; Park et al., 2022).

Within the proposed framework, curvature is interpreted as a measure of inflection intensity, signaling accelerated changes in the direction of project evolution that may be associated with emerging instability, strategic pivots, or major managerial interventions. Torsion captures departures from planar trade-off behavior, revealing multidimensional coupling and potential misalignment among performance and complexity dimensions. Together, these geometric descriptors provide a compact and continuous representation of regime change, structural conflict, and subsequent stabilization in complex projects.

Rather than proposing a new performance metric, this study reframes project monitoring as the observation of project motion through a joint performance–complexity space. In this sense, the SCI–Frenet framework aligns with interpretative and sensemaking-oriented views of project control, where the objective is not precise prediction but enhanced understanding

of unfolding dynamics under complexity (Williams, 1999; Williams, 2005). The framework is therefore intended as a complementary analytical lens that enriches existing project control approaches rather than replacing established KPI-based systems.

The objectives of this study are twofold: (i) to introduce a conceptual and methodological framework that reconceptualizes project monitoring as the analysis of trajectories with intrinsic geometric properties; and (ii) to demonstrate its applicability through a real project case, illustrating how curvature and torsion align with documented project events and managerial interventions. The contributions of this paper are threefold: (1) a conceptual contribution that frames project evolution as a geometric process rather than a sequence of discrete states; (2) a methodological contribution that provides a reproducible, model-agnostic procedure to derive curvature and torsion from KPI and SCI data; and (3) an applied contribution showing how geometric indicators can enrich early-warning interpretation and post-intervention assessment in complex project environments.

The remainder of the paper is structured as follows. Section 2 reviews the Frenet–Serret framework and its relevance for representing dynamic behavior. Section 3 develops the proposed conceptual framework linking geometric descriptors to project management constructs. Section 4 details the methodology used to construct continuous trajectories and compute geometric indicators. Section 5 presents results from a real project application. Section 6 discusses implications, limitations, and boundary conditions. Section 7 concludes and outlines directions for future research.

2. Literature Review (Frenet framework)

2.1. Why a Frenet-based view is relevant for project management

Complex projects behave as interdependent systems in which local changes can propagate and produce non-linear effects that are difficult to anticipate using only traditional control metrics. This has motivated a long-standing call for new paradigms able to represent structural interdependence and dynamic behavior beyond “static” baseline tracking (Williams, 1999). More recent project complexity scholarship continues to emphasize that complexity is not only a matter of size, but also of connectivity, feedback, and emergent behavior, requiring monitoring approaches that can capture how the project system evolves rather than only where it is at reporting points (San Cristóbal, 2018).

In this context, the SCI approach provides a quantitative index of systemic interactions and non-linear amplification/compensation effects at discrete stages (Peris et al., 2025).

However, a core limitation remains: most project datasets are observed at milestones, whereas many critical transitions occur between milestones. The Frenet–Serret apparatus is particularly relevant precisely because it provides intrinsic geometric descriptors of how a trajectory bends and twists through a state space, capturing properties that are invariant to rigid transformations and independent of the specific coordinate representation used to describe the curve.

2.2. Frenet–Serret in engineering trajectories: operational meaning of curvature and torsion

Frenet–Serret concepts (tangent–normal–binormal; curvature κ ; torsion τ) are widely used in engineering domains where a system is naturally represented as a trajectory and decisions depend on anticipating changes in motion or structure. A canonical example is trajectory generation and tracking for autonomous vehicles: Werling et al. (2010) formulate motion planning in a Frenet frame, enabling efficient generation of feasible trajectories relative to a reference path, showing the practical utility of Frenet coordinates as a representation that separates longitudinal progress and lateral deviation. This family of work illustrates two transferable ideas for project management: (i) representing evolution relative to a reference “baseline path” rather than absolute coordinates, and (ii) using curvature-related quantities as indicators of maneuver intensity and constraint interaction.

More broadly, Frenet-based modeling is also common in robotics and kinematics where curvature and torsion support control and stability reasoning (e.g., formation control and orientation control along a curve) (Alvarez et al., 2015). These applications establish Frenet descriptors as a mature mathematical toolkit for detecting and controlling changes in trajectory regimes, an analogy that motivates their adaptation to the monitoring of project evolution in KPI–complexity spaces.

2.3. Frenet–Serret in modern data analysis: from curves as objects to interpretable invariants

In the last decade, Frenet–Serret ideas have also been adopted in statistics and machine learning as a way to handle multidimensional functional data where the “object” of analysis is a curve rather than a scalar time series. Brunel and Park (2019) propose a Frenet–Serret representation for aligning multidimensional curves, explicitly leveraging geometric information to define distances and improve registration of curve-shaped data. This stream is particularly relevant for project monitoring because project histories can be conceptualized as curves embedded in a state space (e.g., cost–time–complexity), and comparisons across projects or across phases are essentially problems of curve comparison and alignment.

Similarly, Laparra et al. (2014) show that nonlinear manifold representations based on curves allow computation of Frenet–Serret frames and generalized curvatures as local geometric features, supporting the view that curvature-like quantities can act as compact descriptors of local structure in high-dimensional data. More recently, research on curvature/torsion estimation for 3D functional data proposes principled approaches to defining mean curvature and mean torsion under a Frenet–Serret characterization, strengthening the methodological foundation for extracting κ and τ robustly from observed curve data (Park, Brunel, & Chassat, 2022). A complementary direction is the synthesis-level treatment of Frenet-based curve analysis in functional/shape data (Chassat, 2023), which consolidates the idea that Frenet features can be estimated, regularized, and interpreted as “shape dynamics” rather than raw derivatives.

Taken together, this literature supports a key methodological point for project applications: curvature and torsion are not merely geometric abstractions; they are increasingly used as interpretable invariants to summarize local change behavior in complex trajectories, especially when linear approximations (e.g., PCA-like models or scalar trend analysis) are insufficient.

2.4. Differential geometry as a lens for systemic behavior in socio-technical systems

Beyond curve geometry, differential geometry has also been used to characterize systemic properties in networks and socio-technical settings. A highly relevant example is the use of Ricci curvature as an indicator of fragility and systemic risk in financial networks (Sandhu, Georgiou, & Tannenbaum, 2016). Although Ricci curvature is a network-geometric concept (not Frenet curvature of a curve), the work demonstrates that geometric invariants can act as meaningful system-level indicators in management-relevant domains, providing a precedent for importing geometry-based indicators into project management when the indicator is carefully operationalized and validated.

This connection is especially important for the present study because SCI itself is conceptually inspired by curvature-like reasoning in differential geometry (Peris et al., 2025).

The Frenet extension proposed in this paper can therefore be interpreted as moving from “curvature-inspired” systemic indexing (SCI) to explicit curvature/torsion descriptors of a project’s path through a KPI–complexity state space.

2.5. Evidence gap: Frenet–Serret is mature in trajectory sciences but undeveloped in project management

An exhaustive search of the peer-reviewed project management literature using combinations of terms such as Frenet, Frenet–Serret, curvature, torsion, and project management reveals no direct adoption of the Frenet–Serret formalism for project monitoring or control.

This gap is consequential: project monitoring research has many tools for performance tracking and discrete milestone assessment, but comparatively few mechanisms to extract continuous “change-of-regime” signals from the evolution of project states, particularly signals that remain interpretable for managerial decision-making. The Frenet–Serret framework addresses precisely this need by producing two intrinsic geometric signals: curvature (change intensity/inflection) and torsion (out-of-plane twisting, interpreted in this paper as multi-dimensional coupling/decoupling among KPI and complexity dimensions). These properties motivate the conceptual framework developed in the next section, where Frenet descriptors are mapped into project management constructs and linked to KPI and SCI measurements.

3. Conceptual Framework: A Frenet–Based Interpretation of Project Dynamics

3.1. From project monitoring to project trajectories

Traditional project monitoring frameworks implicitly assume that project evolution can be understood through independent trends in cost, schedule, quality, or risk (Kerzner, 2015). Even when multiple KPIs are combined into dashboards, the dominant logic remains comparative and discrete: deviations are assessed stage by stage against baselines. However, when projects are viewed as complex adaptive systems, their behavior is better characterized by paths of co-evolution among interdependent dimensions rather than isolated indicator movements (Williams, 2005).

Building on this systemic view, the present framework conceptualizes a project as a trajectory evolving in a multidimensional state space, where each point represents the joint state of selected performance indicators and systemic complexity measures. In this paper, that space is constructed using conventional KPIs (e.g., cost and schedule performance) together with the Systemic Complexity Index (SCI), which captures non-linear interactions among Critical Success Factors (Peris et al., 2025). Instead of asking whether a project is “on track” at a given stage, the focus shifts to how the project is moving through this state space.

Formally, discrete project observations collected at reporting stages are interpreted as samples of an underlying continuous curve $r(t)$. This curve represents the latent project dynamics that unfold between milestones and managerial decisions. The conceptual contribution of this paper lies in arguing that the geometry of this curve contains actionable information about project behavior that is not visible in raw KPI or SCI values alone.

3.2. Why differential geometry: intrinsic versus extrinsic views

A key challenge in modeling project trajectories is avoiding interpretations that depend excessively on scaling, normalization choices, or the particular coordinate system used to

represent KPIs. Differential geometry provides tools to address this challenge by focusing on intrinsic properties of curves, properties that depend on the shape of the trajectory itself rather than on its orientation or coordinate representation in the state space (Do Carmo, 2016).

The Frenet–Serret framework characterizes a smooth curve using:

- a tangent vector, describing the instantaneous direction of evolution,
- a normal vector, indicating the direction of strongest change, and
- a binormal vector, capturing out-of-plane behavior.

From this moving trihedron, two scalar invariants emerge:

- curvature (κ), measuring how sharply the trajectory bends, and
- torsion (τ), measuring how strongly the trajectory twists out of its local plane.

These invariants are well established in engineering and data analysis as descriptors of change intensity and structural coupling, making them particularly suitable for representing project dynamics that are non-linear, path-dependent, and multi-dimensional.

3.3. Interpreting curvature as project inflection intensity

Within the proposed framework, curvature can be interpreted as an indicator of project inflection intensity. High curvature could correspond to rapid changes in the direction of the project trajectory, meaning that the relative contribution of performance dimensions and systemic complexity is shifting quickly.

From a project management perspective, elevated curvature values are interpreted as:

- strategic pivots or replanning episodes,
- emerging crises or accelerating deviations,
- major reallocations of resources or priorities,
- transitions between relatively stable regimes of execution.

Crucially, curvature can increase before individual KPIs reach critical thresholds. A project may still appear “acceptable” in terms of some factors’ performance factors while already exhibiting strong directional changes driven by underlying systemic interactions captured by SCI. In this sense, curvature functions as an early-warning signal of regime change, complementing traditional lagging indicators.

Conversely, low curvature reflects incremental, stable evolution, where performance dimensions evolve in a coordinated manner and the project follows a relatively straight path in the state space.

3.4. Interpreting torsion as multidimensional coupling and trade-off conflict

While curvature captures the intensity of change, it does not reveal whether that change is confined to a dominant trade-off plane or involves deeper structural realignments. This distinction is captured by torsion.

In the proposed conceptualization, torsion is consistent with the degree of multidimensional decoupling among project dimensions. Low torsion suggests that project evolution remains largely planar, meaning that improvements or deteriorations can be explained by relatively stable trade-offs (e.g., cost–time balancing). High absolute torsion values could indicate that the project trajectory is twisting out of this plane, reflecting:

- conflicting optimization across dimensions,
- emergence of new interaction patterns among CSFs,
- misalignment between local KPI improvements and global project stability.

From a managerial standpoint, high torsion highlights situations where local optimization generates systemic tension, such as schedule recovery actions that could disproportionately amplify cost risk or organizational complexity. Torsion therefore acts as an indicator of structural conflict rather than simple performance drift.

3.5. The Frenet trihedron as a decision-support construct

Beyond scalar indicators, the Frenet trihedron itself offers an interpretable geometric decomposition of project dynamics:

- the tangent direction represents the immediate trend of the project,
- the normal direction identifies where corrective pressure is strongest,
- the binormal direction reflects the axis of emerging structural interactions.

Although this paper focuses primarily on curvature and torsion as summary indicators, the full trihedron provides a conceptual basis for future decision-support tools that could visualize not only “how much” change is occurring, but also in which directions corrective actions would be most effective.

3.6. Positioning the SCI–Frenet framework

By embedding the Systemic Complexity Index within a Frenet-based geometric representation, the framework transforms SCI from a static diagnostic into part of a dynamic monitoring system. This enables project managers to reason not only about the magnitude of complexity, but also about the direction, intensity, and structural nature of project evolution over time.

The next section details the methodology used to operationalize this conceptual framework, including the construction of continuous trajectories from discrete project data and the computation of Frenet–Serret invariants.

4. Methodology

This section describes the methodological procedure used to operationalize the proposed SCI–Frenet framework. The methodology is structured as a sequence of well-defined steps that transform discrete project monitoring data into a continuous geometric representation and extract curvature and torsion as dynamic indicators of project behavior. The approach is designed to be reproducible, data-driven, and compatible with standard project control practices.

The methodology assumes that projects are monitored at a finite number of reporting stages or milestones. At each stage, two categories of information are required:

- Key Performance Indicators (KPIs)

KPIs represent normalized measures of project performance along selected dimensions (e.g., cost, schedule). Normalization to a common scale (typically [0,1]) ensures comparability across dimensions and avoids dominance effects in the geometric representation.

- Systemic Complexity Index (SCI)

SCI values are computed following the previously validated methodology, which captures non-linear, cumulative interactions among Critical Success Factors and is evaluated discretely between consecutive project stages.

4.1. Project state vector definition

Let a project observed at discrete reporting stages $k = 1, \dots, N$ be characterized by a vector of selected performance indicators and systemic complexity measures:

$$\mathbf{S}(k) = \left(KPI_1(k), \dots, KPI_p(k), ; SCI_{q_1}(k), \dots, SCI_{q_r}(k) \right).$$

where p denotes the number of selected KPIs included in the state vector, and q_1, \dots, q_r index the Systemic Complexity Indicator (SCI) dimensions considered, so that the project state space has dimension $p + r$.

This general formulation allows the integration of multiple performance and complexity dimensions. In the empirical application presented in this paper, a three-dimensional state space is considered:

$$\mathbf{S}(k) = \left(KPI_{\text{Cost}}(k), ; KPI_{\text{Time}}(k), ; SCI_{\text{Cost,Time}}(k) \right).$$

This selection balances managerial relevance and geometric interpretability, while explicitly incorporating systemic complexity through SCI. The framework is conceptually extensible to higher-dimensional state spaces; however, the classical Frenet–Serret formalism is rigorously defined for three-dimensional trajectories, and extensions beyond this setting require additional geometric constructs.

4.2. Continuous trajectory construction

Project data are typically collected at discrete stages, while geometric analysis requires differentiable curves. To bridge this gap, project stages are parameterized by a continuous variable t (e.g., elapsed time in months), and each component of $\mathbf{S}(k)$ is interpolated independently.

Let $(t_i, x_i)_{i=1}^n$ denote observations of a generic component $x(t)$. A cubic spline interpolation is constructed such that, on each interval $[t_i, t_{i+1}]$,

$$x(t) = S_i(t) = a_i + b_i(t - t_i) + c_i(t - t_i)^2 + d_i(t - t_i)^3, ; t \in [t_i, t_{i+1}], ; i = 1, \dots, n - 1.$$

Spline coefficients are computed to satisfy exact interpolation $S(t_i) = x_i$ and continuity of the function and its first two derivatives (C^2 continuity) at internal knots.

A not-a-knot boundary condition is adopted. Under not-a-knot conditions, continuity of the third derivative is enforced at the first and last internal knots:

$$S_1'''(t_2) = S_2'''(t_2), \quad S_2'''(t_{n-1}) = S_3'''(t_{n-1}).$$

This choice avoids imposing artificial endpoint constraints, such as zero curvature or prescribed slopes, which are rarely justifiable in project management contexts. From a modeling perspective, not-a-knot splines allow the trajectory shape to be driven primarily by observed project data rather than boundary assumptions, yielding more reliable curvature and torsion estimates for detecting systemic inflection points and structural instability.

Applying this procedure to all components yields a smooth parametric trajectory:

$$\mathbf{r}(t) = \mathbf{S}(t) \in \mathbb{R}^3,$$

representing the latent continuous evolution of the project in the KPI–SCI state space.

4.3. Derivative computation

Because each component of $\mathbf{r}(t)$ is a cubic spline, derivatives are available analytically and piecewise. The project trajectory is expressed as:

$$\mathbf{r}(t) = (KPI_C(t), ; KPI_T(t), ; SCI_{CT}(t)).$$

Its derivatives are:

$$\mathbf{r}'(t) = (KPI'_C(t), ; KPI'_T(t), ; SCI'_{CT}(t)),$$

$$\mathbf{r}''(t) = (KPI''_C(t), ; KPI''_T(t), ; SCI''_{CT}(t)),$$

$$\mathbf{r}'''(t) = (KPI'''_C(t), ; KPI'''_T(t), ; SCI'''_{CT}(t)).$$

For a generic spline segment $x(t) = a_i + b_i(t - t_i) + c_i(t - t_i)^2 + d_i(t - t_i)^3$, the derivatives are:

$$x'(t) = b_i + 2c_i(t - t_i) + 3d_i(t - t_i)^2,$$

$$x''(t) = 2c_i + 6d_i(t - t_i),$$

$$x'''(t) = 6d_i,$$

which is constant on each interval. These analytical expressions ensure numerical stability in curvature and torsion computation.

4.4. Frenet–Serret framework

Given the smooth trajectory $\mathbf{r}(t)$, the Frenet–Serret frame is defined as follows:

- Tangent vector: $\mathbf{T}(t) = \frac{\mathbf{r}'(t)}{|\mathbf{r}'(t)|}$
- Curvature: $\kappa(t) = \frac{|\mathbf{r}'(t) \times \mathbf{r}''(t)|}{|\mathbf{r}'(t)|^3}$
- Normal and binormal vectors: $\mathbf{N}(t) = \frac{\mathbf{T}'(t)}{|\mathbf{T}'(t)|}$, $\mathbf{B}(t) = \mathbf{T}(t) \times \mathbf{N}(t)$
- Torsion: $\tau(t) = \frac{(\mathbf{r}'(t) \times \mathbf{r}''(t)) \cdot \mathbf{r}'''(t)}{|\mathbf{r}'(t) \times \mathbf{r}''(t)|^2}$

Curvature $\kappa(t)$ quantifies the intensity of directional change in project evolution, while torsion $\tau(t)$ captures structural decoupling and multidimensional interaction effects among project dimensions.

Although curvature and torsion are defined continuously, project decisions are typically made at discrete reporting stages. Therefore, geometric indicators are evaluated at the corresponding times:

$$\kappa_k = \kappa(t_k), \quad \tau_k = \tau(t_k).$$

This enables direct comparison with KPI deviations, SCI values, and documented project events and managerial interventions. Optional local averaging or smoothing may be applied when the number of stages is small.

The geometric quantities are interpreted as follows:

Table 1. Geometric indicators and their interpretation in project monitoring

Geometric Quantity	Mathematical Meaning	Project Management Interpretation
High κ	Sharp bend in curve	Strategic inflection: major reallocation, crisis, or pivot.
Low κ	Straight path	Stable evolution: incremental progress, low volatility.
High τ	Curve twists out of plane	Systemic instability: factors decoupling, new interactions emerging.
Low τ	Planar motion	Coordinated evolution: factors moving in sync.
$T(t)$	Instantaneous direction	Current trend: where the project is heading next.
$N(t)$	Direction of curvature	Corrective pressure: which factor(s) need adjustment.
$B(t)$	Normal to osculating plane	Interaction plane: the dominant plane of factor co-evolution.

In this sense, the SCI–Frenet model adds a geometric layer to the existing SCI diagnostic:

- SCI answers: What is the level of systemic complexity?
- Frenet answers: How is the project moving through the complexity space?

5. Results (real project application)

5.1. Empirical dataset and input variables

The SCI–Frenet framework was applied to monitoring data from a real project observed across four consecutive stage transitions (2–1, 3–2, 4–3, 5–4). The dataset consists of incremental KPI variations for cost and time, together with aggregated systemic complexity variations obtained from the SCI computation. Negative KPI increments indicate performance deterioration, whereas negative SCI increments indicate reduced systemic complexity (a favorable condition).

Table 2. Incremental KPI and aggregated SCI values per stage transition

Stage	Cost (ΔKPI_C)	$\Sigma SCI(C_j)$	Time (ΔKPI_T)	$\Sigma SCI(T_j)$
2–1	-0.48	0.45	0.51	0.377
3–2	0.093	0.50	0.00	0.387
4–3	0.21	0.00	-0.46	1.000
5–4	0.00	0.39	0.39	0.388

Because the table 2 provides two alternative aggregated SCI series (one associated with cost-related relationships and one with time-related relationships), the geometric results for two 3D project trajectories are reported:

- Cost-SCI trajectory: $\mathbf{r}_C(t) = (\Delta KPI_C(t), \Delta KPI_T(t), \Sigma SCI(C_j)(t))$
- Time-SCI trajectory: $\mathbf{r}_T(t) = (\Delta KPI_C(t), \Delta KPI_T(t), \Sigma SCI(T_j)(t))$

This dual reporting verifies whether the geometric signals are robust to the selection of the SCI aggregation channel.

The four observed stages were parameterized on an equally spaced time axis $t_1 = 1, t_2 = 2, t_3 = 3, t_4 = 4$. Each component of the project state vector was interpolated using cubic splines with not-a-knot boundary conditions, yielding differentiable trajectories $\mathbf{r}_C(t)$ and $\mathbf{r}_T(t)$ in \mathbb{R}^3 . This ensured the existence of analytical first, second, and third derivatives required for curvature and torsion computation.

5.2. Stage-level curvature and torsion results

Curvature $\kappa(t)$ and torsion $\tau(t)$ were evaluated at the stage times ($t = 1,2,3,4$), producing discrete values aligned with managerial decision points.

5.2.1. Results for $\mathbf{r}_C(t) = (\Delta KPI_C, \Delta KPI_T, \Sigma SCI(C_j))$

Table 3. Geometric indicators at stages for $\mathbf{r}_C(t)$

Stage (t)	Transition	$\kappa(t)$	$\tau(t)$
1	2-1	1.25665932	0.02702237
2	3-2	0.88504618	0.27175934
3	4-3	14.92222009	0.64044422
4	5-4	0.09992754	0.06499309

A sharp peak appears at Stage 4-3 ($t=3$) in both curvature and torsion, indicating a major inflection and strong out-of-plane twisting in the project trajectory.

Figure 1. Geometric visualization of project dynamics and regime change in the KPI-SCI space.

Figure 2. Temporal evolution of curvature (κ) along the reconstructed project trajectory

Figure 3. Temporal evolution of torsion (τ) along the reconstructed project trajectory

5.2.2. Results for $r_T(t) = (\Delta KPI_C, \Delta KPI_T, \Sigma SCI(T_j))$

Table 4. Geometric indicators at stages for $r_T(t)$

Stage (t)	Transition	$\kappa(t)$	$\tau(t)$
1	2-1	1.21780472	-0.02007003
2	3-2	0.75755057	-0.20807427
3	4-3	14.13150966	-0.57549960
4	5-4	0.07338467	-0.05427408

The pattern is consistent: the dominant event is again a strong peak at Stage 4-3 ($t=3$), confirming that the geometric signal does not depend on whether the aggregated SCI series is taken from the cost-side or time-side relationships (the sign of torsion changes due to the SCI axis orientation, but the magnitude and peak structure remain aligned).

5.3. Local sensitivity analysis with respect to time parametrization

To provide additional insight into the evolution between stage checkpoints, curvature and torsion were also evaluated at midpoints ($t = 1.5, 2.5, 3.5$). This is not a required reporting mode for project governance but supports interpretation of how the trajectory behaves between formal stages.

Evaluating curvature and torsion at midpoints allows assessing whether the identification of Stage 4-3 as a critical transition is sensitive to the exact choice of evaluation instants. This can be interpreted as a local sensitivity analysis with respect to time parametrization.

5.3.1. Midpoint results for $r_C(t)$

- $t = 1.5$: $\kappa(1.5) = 2.33135366$, $\tau(1.5) = 0.07809263$
- $t = 2.5$: $\kappa(2.5) = 0.83396498$, $\tau(2.5) = 0.77931324$
- $t = 3.5$: $\kappa(3.5) = 1.02994299$, $\tau(3.5) = 0.21042063$

5.3.2. Midpoint results for $r_T(t)$

- $t = 1.5$: $\kappa(1.5) = 2.62152962$, $\tau(1.5) = -0.05833262$
- $t = 2.5$: $\kappa(2.5) = 0.62806836$, $\tau(2.5) = -0.64932637$
- $t = 3.5$: $\kappa(3.5) = 0.80455658$, $\tau(3.5) = -0.18323445$

These midpoint evaluations reinforce that the strongest structural disruption is concentrated around the interval leading into Stage 4–3.

The persistence of the curvature and torsion peak around the 4–3 transition under small temporal shifts suggests that the qualitative conclusions are robust to minor changes in the evaluation grid.

5.4. Interpretation of geometric patterns as results

Across both trajectories, results show three consistent behaviors and align closely with the stage-by-stage evolution observed in the input KPI and SCI increments (table 2).

(i) Early stages: coordinated improvement with limited structural tension (Stages 2–1 and 3–2) From Stage 2–1 to 3–2, the input data indicate: cost performance improves ($\Delta KPI_C = +0.093$), schedule remains stable ($\Delta KPI_T = 0$), and complexity increases only slightly ($\Sigma SCI(C_j) = +0.05$; $\Sigma SCI(T_j) = +0.010$). A classical reading is that the project improves in performance while beginning to introduce additional interactions (e.g., coordination load, organizational changes, or new work fronts). Consistently, the geometric indicators exhibit moderate curvature and low torsion magnitude, which suggests that the trajectory evolves smoothly and largely within a stable trade-off structure (i.e., the system remains governable and changes are not structurally disruptive).

(ii) Critical transition: strong trade-off conflict and systemic regime change (Stage 4–3) From Stage 3–2 to 4–3, the input evolution becomes strongly asymmetric: cost performance improves markedly ($\Delta KPI_C = +0.21$) while time performance deteriorates sharply ($\Delta KPI_T = -0.46$). In parallel, cost-related complexity decreases substantially ($\Sigma SCI(C_j) = -0.50$), whereas time-related complexity increases dramatically ($\Sigma SCI(T_j) = +0.613$). A classical interpretation is that the project optimizes costs at the expense of introducing a large temporal complexity, that could plausibly be associated with replanning, activity overlapping, schedule pressure, or critical task dependencies. This is structurally the most delicate point of the project.

The SCI–Frenet indicators capture this transition unequivocally: both trajectories exhibit an extreme curvature peak at $t = 3$ (Stage 4–3), together with a high torsion magnitude. Geometrically, the project “turns abruptly” in the KPI–SCI space, reflecting a forced reorientation of the system. Importantly, the torsion increase indicates that this is not merely an intense change but a structural decoupling: cost, time, and complexity stop evolving within a single stable plane, revealing a multi-dimensional conflict where improving one subsystem (cost) coincides with instability in another (time and time-related complexity). This is precisely the type of situation where KPIs alone may show what is happening (cost improves while schedule worsens) but do not quantify how structurally dangerous the transition is.

(iii) Post-transition stabilization: recovery of alignment and reduced systemic tension (Stage 5–4). From Stage 4–3 to 5–4, the inputs indicate schedule recovery ($\Delta KPI_T = +0.39$) while cost improvement stalls ($\Delta KPI_C = 0$). Complexity redistributes: cost-related complexity rises again ($\Sigma SCI(C_j) = +0.39$) and time-related complexity drops strongly ($\Sigma SCI(T_j) = -0.612$). A classical reading is that the project regains control of time, potentially through simplification of dependencies, freezing changes, and more rigid management decisions; complexity is shifted away from time and partially absorbed by cost-related structures.

This interpretation is consistent with the geometric response: curvature and torsion both decrease substantially after the Stage 4–3 disruption. The reduction in torsion magnitude suggests improved structural alignment (less decoupling), and the lower curvature reflects a return to a more controlled trajectory. Notably, this stabilization does not necessarily imply simultaneous improvement of all KPIs; rather, it signals a reduction in “systemic chaos” and a restoration of governability, which is consistent with the observed schedule recovery.

The KPI increments describe what changes from stage to stage, but the Frenet descriptors explain how the project moves through the joint performance–complexity space and when that movement becomes structurally risky. In this case, the maximum of κ and $|\tau|$ coincides exactly with the stage where time performance collapses and time-related complexity spikes, and the subsequent reduction in both metrics aligns with the empirical recovery phase. Importantly, the SCI–Frenet model identifies the critical transition purely from the data, without requiring narrative context, supporting its value as a monitoring and early-warning layer.

6. Discussions

Building on the empirical patterns reported in Section 5, this discussion focuses on the theoretical and managerial implications of interpreting curvature and torsion as joint indicators of project regime change, rather than reiterating the stage-level dynamics of the case study.

The results obtained from the real project application provide strong support for the proposed SCI–Frenet framework as a meaningful extension of conventional project monitoring approaches. By representing project evolution as a continuous trajectory in a joint KPI–SCI state space, the framework enables the extraction of geometric indicators, curvature (κ) and torsion (τ), that reveal dynamic and structural properties of project behavior that remain largely invisible to traditional stage-based analyses.

These findings highlight the added value of the SCI–Frenet framework relative not only to KPI- and SCI-based monitoring, but also to established dynamic project approaches such as system dynamics, control-oriented models, network-based risk analysis, and advanced EVM extensions. These approaches have proven valuable for simulation, forecasting, and diagnosis of specific mechanisms driving project performance; however, they typically rely on explicitly specified causal structures, feedback loops, or control assumptions that must be defined *ex ante*. By contrast, KPIs and their extensions primarily describe what happens to performance dimensions, and SCI, despite capturing systemic interactions, remains conventionally static and stage-based. Embedding SCI into a continuous trajectory and analyzing its geometry enables a shift from static diagnosis to dynamic understanding by characterizing how abruptly and how structurally the project system reorients. In the case study, this distinction is illustrated clearly: although not all KPIs improve simultaneously after intervention, the marked reduction in curvature and torsion can be interpreted as restored alignment and governability. This suggests that geometric stabilization may precede, and potentially enable, subsequent performance recovery, positioning curvature and torsion as complementary, model-agnostic indicators of regime change rather than substitutes for existing analytical frameworks.

While the interpretation of curvature and torsion as individual geometric indicators provides valuable insight into project dynamics, managerial sensemaking typically involves reasoning about their joint behavior rather than isolated values. In practice, it is the combination of inflection intensity (curvature) and multidimensional decoupling (torsion) that determines whether observed changes correspond to manageable adjustments, structural conflicts, or stabilization phases.

From a managerial perspective, several practical implications follow. First, increasing curvature and torsion can function as early-warning signals, alerting managers to emerging instability before critical thresholds in KPIs are crossed. Second, torsion provides a direct indication of trade-off conflict, making explicit when improvements in one dimension are achieved at the expense of structural coherence in others. Third, the framework offers a way to assess the effectiveness of managerial interventions: a reduction in geometric indicators signals successful reordering of the project system, even in the presence of short-term performance sacrifices.

To support this interpretive step, Table 5 summarizes typical qualitative patterns arising from different κ - τ configurations and illustrates how these patterns can be mapped to high-level managerial response orientations. Importantly, these responses are not intended as prescriptive rules but as illustrative guidelines that help translate geometric signals into actionable reflection within project governance and decision-making processes. The table should therefore be read as a sensemaking aid rather than a decision algorithm.

Table 5. Interpretation of joint curvature–torsion patterns and their managerial implications

Geometric pattern (κ, τ)	What it typically indicates	Managerial interpretation	Possible response (examples)
High κ, low τ	Abrupt change but mostly planar evolution	Strong inflection within a stable trade-off structure	Tactical adjustment (re-plan locally, reallocate resources, tighten short-term controls)
High κ, high τ	Abrupt change + out-of-plane twisting	Regime change / structural conflict (decoupling across dimensions)	Strategic intervention (re-baseline, governance escalation, redesign interfaces/dependencies)
Low κ, decreasing τ	Smoother evolution + recovering planarity	Stabilization / restored alignment and governability	Consolidate controls (standardize processes, lock scope, monitor for recurrence)

At the same time, several limitations must be acknowledged. The empirical application relies on a small number of reporting stages, which increases sensitivity to interpolation and smoothing choices. Although not-a-knot cubic splines were selected to minimize boundary artifacts and avoid unjustified endpoint assumptions, alternative interpolation schemes or denser data could lead to different numerical values of curvature and torsion. Moreover, while the three-dimensional state space used in this study balances interpretability and analytical power, extending the approach to higher-dimensional spaces raises challenges in visualization and decision support. Finally, the case study is retrospective; prospective validation in live project environments is required to fully assess the framework’s operational and predictive value.

Despite these limitations, the discussion underscores an important theoretical implication: project complexity is not only a property to be measured at discrete points, but a dynamic phenomenon

that unfolds along a trajectory shaped by interdependent decisions and interactions. The SCI–Frenet framework operationalizes this view by connecting systemic complexity theory with differential geometry, demonstrating that geometric invariants such as curvature and torsion can serve as meaningful constructs in the analysis of socio-technical project systems. Overall, the results suggest that geometric analysis does not merely re-express existing indicators but reveals dynamic and structural characteristics of project evolution that remain hidden when performance and complexity are considered in isolation.

7. Conclusions and Future Research

This paper introduced and empirically demonstrated a novel, model-agnostic framework for interpreting project evolution by integrating Systemic Complexity Indicators (SCI) with a trajectory-based representation grounded in the Frenet–Serret formalism. By representing a project as a continuous trajectory in a joint KPI–SCI state space, the proposed SCI–Frenet approach moves beyond static, stage-based assessments and provides an interpretable view of how project dynamics reorient, exhibit instability, and subsequently stabilize over time.

From a conceptual perspective, the main contribution of this work lies in reframing project performance and complexity as geometric objects. Curvature and torsion emerge as intrinsic geometric indicators that capture, respectively, the intensity of directional change and the degree of structural decoupling among project dimensions, while their numerical values reflect the relative scaling and normalization of the underlying KPI and SCI measures. Unlike isolated KPIs or static complexity measures, these indicators reveal whether observed performance changes correspond to smooth adaptation, forced reorientation, or systemic conflict. In the empirical case study, the simultaneous peak of curvature and torsion identified a critical project inflection point that coincided with strong schedule deterioration and a surge in time-related complexity, while the subsequent reduction of both metrics reflected structural stabilization following managerial intervention. Importantly, these signals were obtained directly from the data, without requiring ex post narrative interpretation.

From a practical standpoint, the results suggest that the SCI–Frenet framework can function as a complementary layer to existing project monitoring systems. Curvature and torsion can be interpreted as early-warning and diagnostic indicators, supporting managers in detecting emerging instability, diagnosing trade-off conflicts, and assessing the effectiveness of corrective actions. Rather than replacing KPIs, the framework enriches their interpretation by embedding them in a dynamic and systemic context, thereby enhancing decision-making under complexity.

Despite these contributions, several avenues for future research remain open. First, the framework should be validated on a broader set of projects, spanning different sectors, sizes, and governance structures, to assess its generalizability and to identify typical geometric patterns associated with

different project archetypes. Second, prospective and real-time applications should be explored to evaluate the predictive and operational value of curvature and torsion as early-warning indicators, rather than purely retrospective diagnostics. Third, methodological extensions are needed to study the sensitivity of geometric indicators to data density, interpolation schemes, normalization choices, and noise, as well as to investigate alternative smoothing and filtering techniques.

Further research may also extend the state space beyond three dimensions, incorporating additional KPIs, risk measures, or organizational variables. While the framework is conceptually extensible to higher-dimensional state spaces, the classical Frenet–Serret formalism is rigorously defined for three-dimensional trajectories. Extending the approach to higher dimensions would require generalized curvature descriptors or alternative moving frames, such as Bishop frames, and would introduce additional challenges in both interpretation and visualization. Addressing these extensions constitutes an important direction for future research. Finally, integrating the SCI–Frenet framework with simulation, scenario analysis, or control-oriented project management methods could open new pathways for proactive complexity management, supporting more reflective and sustainable managerial decision-making, helping avoid interventions that shift instability across project dimensions and stakeholders.

In conclusion, this study shows that differential geometry provides a coherent lens for interpreting project dynamics under systemic complexity. By linking performance, complexity, and motion within a unified geometric representation, the SCI–Frenet framework shifts project monitoring from static assessment to dynamic understanding. Its value lies not in predicting outcomes or enabling automated control, but in supporting managerial sensemaking by helping managers recognize when a project is changing its nature rather than merely its performance.

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Appendix A. Computational details (spline construction and full numerical breakdown)

This appendix contains the mathematical derivations, spline coefficients, derivative expressions, and intermediate vector calculations used to obtain the stage-level curvature and torsion values reported in Section 5. The main paper reports only the input data and resulting indicators to preserve readability; the full computational transparency is provided here.

A.1. Time parameterization and finite differences

We used four stages with $t_1 = 1$, $t_2 = 2$, $t_3 = 3$, $t_4 = 4$. Since they are equally spaced, $h_1 = h_2 = h_3 = 1$. For each observed series $x(t_i)$:

$$\delta_i = \frac{x_{i+1} - x_i}{h_i} = x_{i+1} - x_i, \quad i = 1, 2, 3.$$

A.2. Not-a-knot cubic spline system

We construct a cubic spline $S(t)$ that interpolates the points and is C^2 . The not-a-knot condition enforces continuity of the third derivative at the first and last internal knots (t_2 and t_3). With $m_i = S''(t_i)$ and $S_i'''(t) = \frac{m_{i+1} - m_i}{h_i}$, not-a-knot implies:

$$\text{At } t_2: \frac{m_2 - m_1}{h_1} = \frac{m_3 - m_2}{h_2} \Rightarrow -m_1 + 2m_2 - m_3 = 0$$

At t_3 : $\frac{m_3 - m_2}{h_2} = \frac{m_4 - m_3}{h_3} \Rightarrow -m_2 + 2m_3 - m_4 = 0$

For internal nodes the standard spline equations are:

$$h_{i-1}m_{i-1} + 2(h_{i-1} + h_i)m_i + h_im_{i+1} = 6(\delta_i - \delta_{i-1}), \quad i = 2,3.$$

With $h_1 = h_2 = h_3 = 1$:

$$m_1 + 4m_2 + m_3 = 6(\delta_2 - \delta_1)$$

$$m_2 + 4m_3 + m_4 = 6(\delta_3 - \delta_2)$$

Final system (4 equations, 4 unknowns):

$$-m_1 + 2m_2 - m_3 = 0$$

$$m_1 + 4m_2 + m_3 = 6(\delta_2 - \delta_1)$$

$$m_2 + 4m_3 + m_4 = 6(\delta_3 - \delta_2)$$

$$-m_2 + 2m_3 - m_4 = 0$$

Once m_i are obtained, each interval $[t_i, t_{i+1}]$ is:

$S_i(t) = a_i + b_i(t - t_i) + c_i(t - t_i)^2 + d_i(t - t_i)^3$ with:

$$a_i = x_i, \quad c_i = \frac{m_i}{2}, \quad d_i = \frac{m_{i+1} - m_i}{6h_i}, \quad b_i = \delta_i - \frac{h_i}{6}(2m_i + m_{i+1}) \quad \text{and for } h_i = 1, \quad d_i = \frac{m_{i+1} - m_i}{6}.$$

A.3. Splines per variable (solutions and coefficients)

A.3.1. Cost: $\Delta KPI_C(t)$

Data: $x = [-0.48, 0.093, 0.21, 0]$ Finite differences: $\delta_1 = 0.573, \delta_2 = 0.117, \delta_3 = -0.21$

System RHS: $6(\delta_2 - \delta_1) = -2.736, 6(\delta_3 - \delta_2) = -1.962$ Solution: $(m_1, m_2, m_3, m_4) = (-0.585, -0.456, -0.327, -0.198)$

Coefficients (a, b, c, d) :

[1,2]: $(a, b, c, d) = (-0.48, 0.844, -0.2925, 0.0215)$

[2,3]: $(0.093, 0.3235, -0.228, 0.0215)$

[3,4]: $(0.21, -0.068, -0.1635, 0.0215)$

Polynomials:

$$S_1(t) = -0.48 + 0.844(t - 1) - 0.2925(t - 1)^2 + 0.0215(t - 1)^3, \quad t \in [1,2]$$

$$S_2(t) = 0.093 + 0.3235(t - 2) - 0.228(t - 2)^2 + 0.0215(t - 2)^3, t \in [2,3]$$

$$S_3(t) = 0.21 - 0.068(t - 3) - 0.1635(t - 3)^2 + 0.0215(t - 3)^3, t \in [3,4]$$

A.3.2. Time: $\Delta KPI_T(t)$

Data: $x = [0.51, 0, -0.46, 0.39]$ Finite differences: $\delta_1 = -0.51, \delta_2 = -0.46, \delta_3 = 0.85$

RHS: $6(\delta_2 - \delta_1) = 0.30, 6(\delta_3 - \delta_2) = 7.86$ Solution: $(m_1, m_2, m_3, m_4) = (-1.21, 0.05, 1.31, 2.57)$

Coefficients:

[1,2]: $(a, b, c, d) = (0.51, -0.115, -0.605, 0.21)$

[2,3]: $(0, -0.695, 0.025, 0.21)$

[3,4]: $(-0.46, -0.015, 0.655, 0.21)$

A.3.3. $\Sigma SCI(C_j)(t)$

Data: $x = [0.45, 0.50, 0, 0.39]$ Finite differences: $\delta_1 = 0.05, \delta_2 = -0.50, \delta_3 = 0.39$ RHS:

$6(\delta_2 - \delta_1) = -3.30, 6(\delta_3 - \delta_2) = 5.34$ Solution: $(m_1, m_2, m_3, m_4) = (-1.99, -0.55, 0.89, 2.33)$

Coefficients:

[1,2]: $(a, b, c, d) = (0.45, 0.805, -0.995, 0.24)$

[2,3]: $(0.50, -0.465, -0.275, 0.24)$

[3,4]: $(0, -0.295, 0.445, 0.24)$

A.3.4. $\Sigma SCI(T_j)(t)$

Data: $x = [0.377, 0.387, 1, 0.388]$ Finite differences: $\delta_1 = 0.010, \delta_2 = 0.613, \delta_3 = -0.612$

RHS: $6(\delta_2 - \delta_1) = 3.618, 6(\delta_3 - \delta_2) = -7.350$ Solution: $(m_1, m_2, m_3, m_4) = (2.431, 0.603, -1.225, -3.053)$

Coefficients:

[1,2]: $(a, b, c, d) = (0.377, -0.90083333, 1.2155, -0.30466667)$

[2,3]: $(0.387, 0.61616667, 0.3015, -0.30466667)$

[3,4]: $(1, 0.30516667, -0.6125, -0.30466667)$

A.4. Continuity verification (not-a-knot property)

A not-a-knot cubic spline is C^2 at all nodes ($t = 2$ and $t = 3$). Additionally, not-a-knot enforces third derivative continuity:

$$S_1'''(t_2) = S_2'''(t_2) \text{ and } S_2'''(t_3) = S_3'''(t_3).$$

Since $S_i''' = (m_{i+1} - m_i)$ for $h_i = 1$, the constraints $m_2 - m_1 = m_3 - m_2$ and $m_3 - m_2 = m_4 - m_3$ are equivalent to:

$$-m_1 + 2m_2 - m_3 = 0 \text{ and } -m_2 + 2m_3 - m_4 = 0.$$

Example (Cost): $m_2 - m_1 = 0.129$, $m_3 - m_2 = 0.129$, $m_4 - m_3 = 0.129 \Rightarrow S_1''' = S_2''' = S_3''' = 0.129$.

A.5. Frenet–Serret curvature and torsion computation (full breakdown)

A.5.1. Definitions and trajectory variants

Curvature and torsion are:

$$\kappa(t) = \frac{|\mathbf{r}'(t) \times \mathbf{r}''(t)|}{|\mathbf{r}'(t)|^3}$$

$$\tau(t) = \frac{\mathbf{r}'(t) \cdot (\mathbf{r}''(t) \times \mathbf{r}'''(t))}{|\mathbf{r}'(t) \times \mathbf{r}''(t)|^2}$$

Two trajectories are evaluated:

$$\mathbf{r}_C(t) = (\Delta KPI_C(t), \Delta KPI_T(t), \Sigma SCI(C_j)(t))$$

$$\mathbf{r}_T(t) = (\Delta KPI_C(t), \Delta KPI_T(t), \Sigma SCI(T_j)(t))$$

A.5.2. Derivatives from spline segments

For $S_i(t) = a_i + b_i(t - t_i) + c_i(t - t_i)^2 + d_i(t - t_i)^3$:

$$S_i'(t) = b_i + 2c_i(t - t_i) + 3d_i(t - t_i)^2$$

$$S_i''(t) = 2c_i + 6d_i(t - t_i)$$

$$S_i'''(t) = 6d_i \text{ (constant per interval)}$$

Vector derivatives:

$$\mathbf{r}'(t) = (x'(t), y'(t), z'(t)), \mathbf{r}''(t) = (x''(t), y''(t), z''(t)), \mathbf{r}'''(t) = (x'''(t), y'''(t), z'''(t)).$$

A.5.3. Cross product and norms

$$\mathbf{r}' \times \mathbf{r}'' = (y'z'' - z'y'', z'x'' - x'z'', x'y'' - y'x'')$$

$$|\mathbf{r}' \times \mathbf{r}''| = \sqrt{(y'z'' - z'y'')^2 + (z'x'' - x'z'')^2 + (x'y'' - y'x'')^2}$$

$$|\mathbf{r}'| = \sqrt{(x')^2 + (y')^2 + (z')^2}$$

A.5.4. Full stage-by-stage numerical evaluation

Trajectory $\mathbf{r}_C(t)$

$$\begin{aligned} t=1 \text{ (Stage 2-1)} \quad & \mathbf{r}'(1) = (0.8440, -0.1150, 0.8050) \quad \mathbf{r}''(1) = (-0.5850, -1.2100, -1.9900) \\ & \mathbf{r}'''(1) = (0.1290, 1.2600, 1.4400) \quad \mathbf{r}' \times \mathbf{r}'' = (1.202900, 1.208635, -1.088515) \quad |\mathbf{r}'| = \\ & 1.172001, \quad |\mathbf{r}' \times \mathbf{r}''| = 2.023025 \quad \kappa(1) = 1.25665932, \quad \tau(1) = 0.02702237 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} t=2 \text{ (Stage 3-2)} \quad & \mathbf{r}'(2) = (0.3235, -0.6950, -0.4650) \quad \mathbf{r}''(2) = (-0.4560, 0.0500, -0.5500) \\ & \mathbf{r}'''(2) = (0.1290, 1.2600, 1.4400) \quad \mathbf{r}' \times \mathbf{r}'' = (0.405500, 0.389965, -0.300745) \quad |\mathbf{r}'| = \\ & 0.896606, \quad |\mathbf{r}' \times \mathbf{r}''| = 0.637927 \quad \kappa(2) = 0.88504618, \quad \tau(2) = 0.27175934 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} t=3 \text{ (Stage 4-3)} \quad & \mathbf{r}'(3) = (-0.0680, -0.0150, -0.2950) \quad \mathbf{r}''(3) = (-0.3270, 1.3100, 0.8900) \\ & \mathbf{r}'''(3) = (0.1290, 1.2600, 1.4400) \quad \mathbf{r}' \times \mathbf{r}'' = (0.373100, 0.156985, -0.093985) \quad |\mathbf{r}'| = \\ & 0.303107, \quad |\mathbf{r}' \times \mathbf{r}''| = 0.415549 \quad \kappa(3) = 14.92222009, \quad \tau(3) = 0.64044422 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} t=4 \text{ (Stage 5-4)} \quad & \mathbf{r}'(4) = (-0.3305, 1.9250, 1.3150) \quad \mathbf{r}''(4) = (-0.1980, 2.5700, 2.3300) \\ & \mathbf{r}'''(4) = (0.1290, 1.2600, 1.4400) \quad \mathbf{r}' \times \mathbf{r}'' = (1.105700, 0.509695, -0.468235) \quad |\mathbf{r}'| = \\ & 2.354587, \quad |\mathbf{r}' \times \mathbf{r}''| = 1.304456 \quad \kappa(4) = 0.09992754, \quad \tau(4) = 0.06499309 \end{aligned}$$

Trajectory $\mathbf{r}_T(t)$ (analogous full evaluation)

$$t=1: \kappa(1) = 1.21780472, \quad \tau(1) = -0.02007003$$

$$t=2: \kappa(2) = 0.75755057, \quad \tau(2) = -0.20807427$$

$$t=3: \kappa(3) = 14.13150966, \quad \tau(3) = -0.57549960$$

$$t=4: \kappa(4) = 0.07338467, \quad \tau(4) = -0.05427408$$

A.6. Summary of spline coefficients

Cost (ΔKPI_C):

$$[1,2]: (a, b, c, d) = (-0.48, 0.844, -0.2925, 0.0215)$$

$$[2,3]: (0.093, 0.3235, -0.228, 0.0215)$$

$$[3,4]: (0.21, -0.068, -0.1635, 0.0215)$$

Time (ΔKPI_T):

$$[1,2]: (0.51, -0.115, -0.605, 0.21)$$

$$[2,3]: (0, -0.695, 0.025, 0.21)$$

$$[3,4]: (-0.46, -0.015, 0.655, 0.21)$$

$\Sigma SCI(C_j)$:

$$[1,2]: (0.45, 0.805, -0.995, 0.24)$$

[2,3]: (0.50, -0.465, -0.275, 0.24)

[3,4]: (0, -0.295, 0.445, 0.24)

$\Sigma SCI(T_j)$:

[1,2]: (0.377, -0.90083333, 1.2155, -0.30466667)

[2,3]: (0.387, 0.61616667, 0.3015, -0.30466667)

[3,4]: (1, 0.30516667, -0.6125, -0.30466667)